

1 Running head: BACTERIOLOGY VS. PCR IN SHEEP AND GOATS

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3 **Identifying the major bacteria causing intramammary infections in individual milk**
4 **samples of sheep and goats using traditional bacteria culturing and real-time**
5 **polymerase chain reaction**

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ABSTRACT

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Use of DNA-based methods, such as real-time PCR, has increased sensitivity and shortened time for bacteria identification, compared to traditional bacteriology; however, results should be interpreted carefully because a positive PCR result does not necessarily mean that there is an infection. One-hundred and eight lactating dairy ewes (56 Manchega and 52 Lacaune) and 24 Murciano-Granadina dairy goats were used for identifying the main bacteria causing intramammary infections (IMI) using traditional bacterial culturing and real-time PCR and their effects on milk performances. Udder half milk samples were taken for bacterial culture and somatic cell count (SCC) 3 times throughout lactation. IMI was assessed based on bacteria isolated in ≥ 2 samplings accompanied by increased SCC. Prevalence of subclinical IMI was 42.9% in Manchega, 50.0% Lacaune and 41.7% in goats, estimated milk yield loss being 13.1, 17.9 and 18.0%, respectively. According to bacteriology results, 87% of the identified single bacteria colonies or culture-negative growth were repeatable throughout samplings, which agreed 98.9% with the PCR results. Nevertheless, the study emphasized that one sampling may not be sufficient to determine IMI and therefore, other inflammatory responses such as increased SCC should be monitored to identify true infections. Moreover, when PCR methodology is used, aseptic and precise milk sampling procedure is the key for avoiding false positive amplifications. In conclusion, both PCR and bacterial culture methods proved to have similar accuracy for identifying infective bacteria in sheep and goats. The final choice will depend on their response time and cost analysis, according to the requirements and farm management strategy.

Key words: mastitis prevalence, small ruminant, subclinical mastitis, real-time polymerase chain reaction

INTRODUCTION

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52 Milk provides the major source of income in dairy farms. Therefore, every disturbance
53 in producing optimal milk quantity and milk quality will reduce farm profitability. Milk
54 quantity and quality are related to genetics (i.e., breed) and environment (i.e., nutrition and
55 management) as well as to animal health (i.e., udder health). Small ruminant production
56 systems vary widely, from traditional hand milking to the most modern computerized
57 milking parlors, and with different dairy breeds, herd sizes and levels of milk yield. Despite
58 these differences, all sheep and most goat milk is destined for manufacturing dairy products.
59 Therefore, milk quality is a key for high quality dairy products, the intramammary infected
60 milk compromising its manufacturing ability (e.g., rennet coagulation and curd firmness)
61 for dairy products.

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Intramammary infection is one of the main causes of milk production losses (Gonzalo et
63 al., 2002; Leitner et al., 2007, 2008) along with changes in its composition (Leitner et al.,
64 2004a,b). In addition, IMI influences milk coagulation properties depending on the species
65 of bacteria (Leitner et al., 2006). Of the bacteria involved, some cause clinical infection,
66 while the majority cause only subclinical infection with no visible signs. Consequently, in
67 order to identify infected animals, as well as the infecting bacteria, milk sampling and
68 laboratory diagnoses are needed. However, these methods are expensive and the time of
69 sampling is crucial. Conventional bacterial culturing often requires 48 to 72 h for
70 incubation, and additional confirmation tests that takes time to be completed (National
71 Mastitis Council, 1999). On the other hand, polymerase chain reaction (**PCR**) assay kits
72 available on the market for mastitis testing does not require a culture step and can be
73 performed in 3 to 4 h total (Koskinen et al., 2009). Nevertheless, current prices per sample
74 range around \$25 to 30. In clinical mastitis, such rapid results should shorten the total
75 duration of treatment, improve the therapeutic outcome, and decrease unnecessary use of
76 antimicrobials (Pyörälä, 2002; Barkema et al., 2006). For clinical cases of mastitis, the early

77 detection is decisive to help animals to heal and to apply veterinary treatment if necessary.
78 On the other hand, with regard to subclinical infection, time of laboratory diagnostic
79 procedure is not crucial for chronic forms; however, justification of sampling and testing
80 are based on cost-benefit analysis aiming to improve milk yield and composition.

81 Bacterial identification by inoculating milk on agar plates is the gold standard of
82 classical bacteriology (Oliver et al., 2004). In the last 20 yr, while DNA based methods
83 such as real-time PCR and other methods on the market have increased the sensitivity and
84 shortened the time needed for bacteria identification, costs remained relatively high. In
85 addition, interpretation of the PCR results is questionable because it may either contain
86 more than one bacteria species or give false-positive results for animals free of
87 inflammation (Koskinen et al., 2010). Possible causes of PCR false-positive could be: low
88 number of bacterial shedding (i.e., less than 3 cfu), microorganism no growing in the culture
89 media or contaminated milk (i.e., bacteria coming from other sources). Hence, positive
90 results in a sample of more than a single bacteria from known clinical and subclinical
91 infected glands, or from glands with no inflammation but showing increased somatic cell
92 count (SCC) or altered cell distribution, may be either true positive or derived from
93 extramammary contamination of bacteria inhabiting on udder skin and teat canal (Taponen
94 et al., 2009).

95 The objectives of the current study were to: 1) compare the identification of the main
96 bacteria causing clinical and subclinical IMI in individual milk samples taken from sheep
97 and goats udder-halves, using traditional bacterial culturing (BAC) and real-time PCR,
98 and 2) study the influence of IMI on milk yield and SCC of dairy sheep and goats.

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MATERIAL AND METHODS

101 *Animals*

102 The study was conducted at the Experimental Farm of the SGCE (Servei de Granges i
103 Camps Experimentals) of the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB, Bellaterra,
104 Spain). The Ethical Committee on Animal and Human Experimentation (CEEAH) of the
105 UAB approved all the experimental and animal care procedures.

106 A total of 108 lactating dairy sheep (parity, 2.9 ± 0.2) of two breeds (Manchega, MN; n
107 = 56; Lacaune; LC, n = 52) and 24 Murciano-Granadina dairy goats (parity, 4.0 ± 1.0) were
108 studied after the weaning of the lambs and after parturition, respectively. Animals were kept
109 under a semi-confinement system, allowed to graze for 6-h daily in an annual Italian rye-
110 grass pasture and supplemented indoors with alfalfa hay *ad libitum* (1.27 Mcal of NE_L/kg
111 and 20.1% CP; DM basis) and concentrate at a flat rate of 0.8 kg/d (1.75 Mcal NE_L/kg and
112 16.5% CP; DM basis) distributed during milking. Water and a commercial block of
113 vitamins and minerals (Multi-Block, Agraria Comarcal del Vallès, Les Franqueses,
114 Barcelona, Spain) were permanently available in the shelter.

115 Ewes were machine milked twice-daily (0800 and 1700 h) in a double-12 stall parallel
116 low-line milk pipeline milking parlor (Westfalia Surge Iberica, Granollers, Spain) equipped
117 with recording jars and electronic pulsators at a vacuum of 42 kPa, 120 pulses/min and 50%
118 pulsation ratio. Goats were milked once a day (0900) in the same milking parlor using
119 different electronic pulsators (90 pulses/min and 60% pulsation ratio). The milking routine
120 included machine milking, without udder preparation, but with post milking teat dipping in
121 an iodine solution (P3-ioshield, Ecolab Hispano-Portuguesa, Barcelona, Spain) after cluster
122 removal. Milk yield of individual ewes was recorded weekly at each milking from the
123 weaning of the lambs (35 days in milk, DIM) to 120 and 135 DIM for MN and LC,
124 respectively. For goats, individual milk yield was recorded weekly from 7 to 280 DIM.

125

126 ***Milk sampling***

127 Milk samples were taken aseptically by hand milking during the morning milking and
128 submitted to the laboratory within 2 h. Prior to sampling, teats were disinfected by dipping
129 in a iodine solution (P3-ioshield) and dried with disposable paper towels. The first 3 milk
130 squirts were discarded. Following cleaning, the teats were disinfected by 70% ethanol and
131 left for approximately 1 min to evaporate any remaining alcohol. Milk of the first squirts
132 were again discarded and 3 to 4 mL samples were collected from each udder-half into sterile
133 tubes (Eurotubo Deltalab, code 429946, Rubí, Spain) for bacteriological testing done on the
134 same day and California mastitis test (CMT) examination *in situ* (Drofilisa, Fatro Ibérica,
135 Sant Just Desvern, Spain). Following milking, milk yield of each gland was recorded
136 individually and, after mixing the total amount collected, 40 mL milk were sampled and
137 preserved with bronopol (Broad Spectrum Microtabs II, D & F Control Systems Inc., San
138 Ramon, CA) for SCC using a Fossomatic 5000 (Foss Electric, Hillerød, Denmark) at the
139 Interprofessional Milk Laboratory of Catalonia (ALLIC, Cabrils, Barcelona, Spain). These
140 procedures were repeated 3 times during lactation (50 to 90 DIM, at approximately 15-d
141 intervals). For comparing BAC and real-time PCR, an additional milk sample (4 mL) was
142 taken in sterile tubes from selected glands at the second and third sampling period and
143 stored frozen at -20°C until analyzed at the ALLIC laboratory. Positive gland infection was
144 based on bacteria isolation in at least 2 of the 3 samplings accompanied by an increase of
145 somatic cells (CMT and/or SCC).

146 Udder health was also visually evaluated before sampling according to a subjective
147 classification based on gland morphology while animals were in the milking parlor:
148 symmetrical (normal udder with no hardness at palpation), asymmetrical (abnormal udder
149 with or without hardness in at least one gland), or involuted (< 250 mL/d of milk).

150 Animals were classified according to udder health as follows: 1) **NBF** (udders with no
151 bacterial finding and CMT score ≤ 1), 2) **IMI-1** (udders with bacterial finding and CMT

152 score >1 in one half), and 3) IMI-2 (udders with bacterial finding and CMT score >1 in both
153 halves).

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155 ***Bacteriological Examinations***

156 Bacteriological analyses were performed separately at the UAB (**BAC1**), in fresh milk,
157 and at the ALLIC (**BAC2**), in frozen samples, according to accepted standards (Oliver et
158 al., 2004). At BAC1, 0.01 mL were streaked onto blood-agar plates (Bacto-Agar, Difco
159 Laboratory, Le Pont de Claix, France) containing 5% of washed sheep red blood cells.
160 Plates were incubated at 37 °C and examined for bacterial growth after 18 and 42 h. At
161 BAC2, 20 µL of milk were streaked on esculin blood agar (Tryptone soy agar, Biokar
162 Diagnostics-Solabia, Pantin, France; and esculin, Merck Millipore, Darmstadt, Germany)
163 and incubated at 37°C for 48 h with readings at 24 and 48 h. Cultures of colonies initially
164 picked from the blood agar were tested by coagulase test *in situ* (Baird Parker RPF, Biokar
165 Diagnostics) and Tryptone Bile X-Glucuronide BX selective agar (Chromocult, Merck
166 Millipore). Samples were subjected to: gram stain, catalase, esculin hydrolysis (*in situ*),
167 CAMP factor hemolysis and agglutination tests for pathogen identification according to
168 microbiology reference methods.

169

170 ***Real-time polymerase chain reaction***

171 Identification of bacterial DNA was done using a real-time PCR based commercial
172 reagent kit (PathoProof Mastitis Complete-12 kit PCR Assay, Thermo Fisher Scientific,
173 Vantaa, Finland) for direct analysis of all milk samples at the ALLIC laboratory. The
174 PathoProof kit for accurate identification of mastitis-causing bacteria from bovine milk can
175 identify the following prevailing mastitis causing bacterial species and groups:
176 *Staphylococcus* spp. (including *S. aureus* and all major coagulase-negative staphylococci
177 (**CNS**)), *Streptococcus* (*S. dysgalactiae*, *S. agalactiae* and *S. uberis*), *Escherichia coli*,

178 *Enterococcus* spp. (including *E. faecalis* and *E. faecium*), *Klebsiella* spp. (including *K.*
 179 *oxytoca* and *K. pneumoniae*), *Serratia marcescens*, *Corynebacterium bovis*, *Arcanobacter*
 180 *pyogenes* and *Peptoniphilus (Peptostreptococcus) indolicus*, as well as the assay targeted
 181 the *Staphylococcal* β -lactamase penicillin resistance gene *blaZ*.

182 The assay was carried out following the manufacturer's procedure (PathoProof) and
 183 included all necessary reagents for DNA extraction and real-time PCR. The DNA extraction
 184 method used 350 μ L milk as the starting volume and involved an enzymatic lysis step,
 185 disrupting the cell walls of gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria, as well as spin
 186 column-based DNA purification and elution steps.

187

188 *Statistical Analyses*

189 Statistical analyses were carried out with JMP software (SAS Institute, 2000). The
 190 experimental unit was the individual animal. For sheep, the analyzed parameters were milk
 191 yield and log SCC by a three-way ANOVA model:

$$192 \quad Y_{ijkl} = \mu + \alpha_i + \beta_j + \delta_k + \alpha\beta_{ij} + \alpha\delta_{ik} + \beta\delta_{jk} + e_{ijkl}.$$

193 where: μ = overall mean, α_i = breed (MN or LC), β_j = IMI status (NBF, IMI-1, or IMI-2),
 194 δ_k = parity (1, 2, 3 or ≥ 4), $\alpha\beta_{ij}$ = breed \times IMI status interaction, $\alpha\delta_{ik}$ = breed \times parity
 195 interaction, $\beta\delta_{jk}$ = IMI status \times parity interaction, and e_{ijkl} = residual error. The breed \times IMI
 196 status \times parity number interaction was not included in the model due to a missing
 197 combination (no MN sheep in the 1st lactation with IMI-2).

198 For goats, breed effect was excluded from the model. Multiple comparisons between
 199 means were done by Tukey's Honestly-significant-difference test and significance
 200 declared at $P < 0.05$, unless otherwise indicated. Correlations between all the continuous
 201 variables and the analyzed parameters were determined for all data.

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RESULTS

204 ***Milk Production and SCC Score***

205 The MN ewes produced less milk than LC sheep ($P < 0.001$) as shown in Table 1. Breed
206 had no effect on SCC levels ($P = 0.383$) but IMI status affected milk yield and SCC score
207 of udder halves ($P < 0.001$). The log SCC of uninfected milk samples ranged between 4.96
208 and 5.22 whereas they ranged between 6.56 and 6.80 for the ewes with IMI-2 (Table 1).
209 Figure 1 illustrates the individual MN and LC log SCC values according to IMI status.

210 For each sheep breed, animals with IMI-2 showed significantly lower milk yield than
211 NBF ($P < 0.001$) but no differences were found between IMI-2 and IMI-1 ($P > 0.05$; Table
212 1). There were no significant interactions except for the case of breed \times SCC ($P = 0.032$)
213 in which the LC SCC values were greater. Milk yield increased according to parity in both
214 breeds ($P < 0.001$) but SCC did not vary ($P = 0.840$).

215 Infected goats tended to produce less milk ($P = 0.080$) and had slightly higher SCC
216 than uninfected goats (Table 1; $P < 0.05$), as shown in Figure 1. No correlation was found
217 between milk yield and SCC in both sheep and goats.

218

219 ***Bacteria Isolation***

220 Throughout the study, only 3 (2.8%) ewes were diagnosed with clinical mastitis, 2 were
221 infected with *E. coli* and 1 was infected with *Pseudomonas spp.* Clinical mastitis was
222 treated after sampling and those animals have been excluded from the study thereafter.
223 Comparing the BAC results, 87% of the udder halves were thrice identical either for single
224 bacteria colonies or no NBF and 11% only repeated in two samplings. Moreover, 2% of
225 samples showed contaminated milk in at least one of the samplings (more than 2 colony
226 types per plate). According to BAC results, 17 MN ewes were IMI-1 and 7 IMI-2, resulting
227 in 42.9% subclinically infected ewes (Table 1). On the other hand, 17 LC ewes were IMI-
228 1 and 9 were IMI-2, resulting in 50.0% of ewes that were subclinically infected. Two-thirds

229 of the infected glands were asymmetrical. Regarding the uninfected sheep, 89.7% had
230 symmetrical udders and 10.3% had asymmetrical ones (4 MN and 2 LC ewes).

231 Of the 24 Murciano-Granadina goats, 1 doe (4.2%) was diagnosed with clinical mastitis
232 caused by *E. coli*. Eight were found uninfected (33.3%) with symmetrical udders, 10 were
233 IMI-1 (of which 2 had asymmetrical glands) and 3 were IMI-2 with symmetrical glands
234 (Table 1). Two more goats had high SCC in one of the glands with no bacterial finding.

235

236 ***Comparison of Bacterial Culture and Real-Time PCR of Individual Milk Samples***

237 A total of 90 milk samples from both breeds of sheep and goats were selected from
238 individual glands with known bacterial infection (IMI-1 and IMI-2) and from uninfected
239 glands with low SCC (NBF with CMT = 0) or high SCC (NBF with CMT > 1). Results of
240 the bacterial culturing are summarized in Table 2. Of the 90 samples, including sheep of
241 both breeds and goats, 30 (33.7%) were NBF, of which 18 with low SCC and 12 with high
242 SCC. Regardless of CMT, all 30 NBF samples were confirmed by bacteriology (BAC1 and
243 BAC2) and 29 by real-time PCR as NBF. Only a single NBF sample was found positive by
244 real-time PCR for *Staphylococcus spp.* (Table 2) and considered as BAC false negative.

245 Of the 60 infected samples, 38 were identified as CNS species in BAC1 and BAC2
246 (Table 2). The real-time PCR results mainly agreed with BAC, 36 samples being classified
247 as *Staphylococcus spp.* or *Staphylococcus spp.* and β -lactamase by PCR, and the remaining
248 2 samples were identified as no CNS (*S. aureus* and *S. uberis*).

249 Eight more samples were identified as *S. aureus* in BAC1 and BAC2, of which 7
250 matched *S. aureus* and 1 *Staphylococcus spp.* by real-time PCR. Moreover, 5 isolates
251 identified as *Streptococcus spp.* by BAC1 and BAC2 failed to be confirmed by real-time
252 PCR despite being sensitive to *S. agalactiae*, *S. dysgalactiae* and *S. uberis*.

253 Of the remaining isolates, identified by BAC1 and BAC2 as 2 *A. pyogenes*, 2 *E. coli* and
254 3 *Enterococcus spp.*, all were confirmed with certainty by real-time PCR. Finally, PCR
255 failed to identify 2 BAC1 and BAC2 as *Enterobacteriaceae*.

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DISCUSSION

258 Despite the low incidence of clinical IMI in this study, the subclinical IMI prevalence
259 indicated that nearly 4 of 10 ewes or goats showed signs of udder inflammation, as
260 measured by SCC, CMT and bacteriology. Prevalence of clinical mastitis in dairy sheep is
261 generally < 5% (Berger et al., 2004), as observed in our data, but prevalence of subclinical
262 mastitis infections were in 21% glands and 34% ewes according to Las Heras et al. (1999).
263 Cuccuru et al. (2011) reported in sheep an increase of subclinical IMI prevalence with
264 parity, varying from 35 to 65% for second to fifth, respectively. Prevalence of subclinical
265 infections in dairy goats range from 7 to 34% of the glands and 17 to 44% of the goats
266 (Contreras et al., 1995). It is generally accepted that 20 to 30% milk samples from IMI
267 glands result in no growth by bacterial culturing in dairy cows (Bradley et al., 2007;
268 Koskinen et al., 2010).

269 Many animals which were found subclinically infected in our study had normal udders
270 without signs of IMI (no detectable changes in the milk, the udder or the animal) but with
271 increased SCC levels. Asymmetrical udders in uninfected sheep and goats also have high
272 SCC, probably as a result of previous infections. These results indicate that (i) by adequate
273 and careful aseptic milk sampling, it is possible to detect a few bacteria type in BAC and/or
274 real-time PCR in most samples; (ii) a positive bacteriological result alone is not a sufficient
275 indication of IMI and should always be coupled with an inflammatory response test (e.g.,
276 SCC or CMT), and (iii) not all inflammation responses as measured by SCC or CMT are
277 indications of the presence of bacteria (i.e., IMI). Therefore, adequate milk sampling for
278 standard bacteriology in combination with an inflammatory response test, are necessary in

279 order to identify true mammary infections. Moreover, in case of disagreement between the
280 two tests, second and third samplings are needed.

281 Real-time PCR assay was performed on milk samples without the need of bacterial
282 culturing. High agreement between the BAC, performed independently by 2 laboratories
283 (BAC1 and BAC2) and the real-time PCR was found in the present study. Moreover, udders
284 presumed to be uninfected by BAC and with low milk SCC, were detected as NBF by PCR.

285 These results were confirmed by those obtained by independent BAC tests which found
286 98.9% agreement between them and, whenever the real-time PCR was positive, a single
287 bacterium was detected. Moreover, 1/30 (3%) of samples identified as NBF by BAC were
288 positive as *Staphylococcus spp.* by real-time PCR. The advantage of the real-time PCR was
289 its ability to differentiate between β -lactam positive and negative CNS species. This
290 information is of extreme importance since approximately half of the CNS are β -lactam
291 positive (i.e., resistant to penicillin). However, it does not mean that the entire β -lactam
292 negative are sensitive to it, because more than one gene is involved in the drug resistance,
293 and consequently in the efficacy of antibiotics. The β -lactam negative *S. aureus* found in
294 this study do not guarantee drug resistance and therefore can be considered sensitive. The
295 real-time PCR failed to identify the 5 *Streptococci* spp., probably because they are different
296 from the 3 *Streptococci* species detectable by the kit used (i.e., *S. agalactia*, *S. dysgalactiae*
297 and *S. uberis*). All in all, the real-time PCR commercial kit results were almost identical to
298 those of BAC, and produced an outcome in a few hours compared to days needed for
299 conventional bacteriology. However, the real-time PCR disadvantages are bacterial species
300 limitations for which the diagnostic kit was designed (bovine-specific) and the high cost of
301 the test, which could currently limit its use.

302 Our results disagree with previous studies using the same kit comparing bacterial
303 cultures and real-time PCR in bovine milk samples. Real-time PCR provided
304 bacteriological diagnosis for almost 50% of the negative results obtained from conventional

305 culturing of mastitic milk samples (Taponen et al., 2009). Koskinen et al. (2010), using
306 1,000 cow samples, identified more than 15% of the clinical and subclinical quarters with
307 2 or more bacteria species using BAC, whereas the PCR identified around 50% of the same
308 samples. Moreover, of the healthy quarters with low SCC, one third of the samples were
309 positive, mostly with one bacterial species tested by the PCR.

310 The sensitivity and reliability of the two methods used for bacterial detection mainly
311 depend on a set of key factors such as: (i) secretion of bacteria is not uniform through
312 repeated milk sampling; therefore, a low bacteria count can show a negative result
313 especially in BAC, (ii) the teat end is colonized with different bacteria, including mastitis
314 pathogens, thus small amounts of bacterial DNA, detectable by PCR, may end in false-
315 positive results. Thus, one sampling may not be sufficient to determine an infected gland
316 and therefore, inflammation response such as increase in SCC and change in their
317 distribution is essential. Moreover, if DNA methodology is used, sampling is the key to
318 avoid contamination, and (iii) both methods are not feasible outside reference laboratories,
319 but more of a limitation exists if a specific DNA kit is used (i.e., aerobic bacteria in BAC
320 or pathogens in DNA specific kit).

321 Cost-benefit of commercial clinical and subclinical diagnostic tests can rely on control
322 studies. In clinical mastitis, the time of the diagnostic test results is important and in most
323 cases the number of the causative bacteria is high, therefore, DNA methods are preferred.
324 Thus, time of sampling and testing (in hours) are important in the treatment decision. In
325 subclinical mastitis, time of the diagnostic procedure is not crucial so that the cost of
326 diagnostics, the tools for coping with the infection and the influence of the infection on
327 productivity must to be considered in making the decision. Antibiotic treatment of animals
328 that are not at risk (as in the case of clinical mastitis) needs to be justified with respect to
329 the costs of medicine and milk losses (Barlow et al., 2009; van den Borne et al., 2010) as
330 well as the occurrences of hazards to consumer's health and safety. Therefore, diagnosis

331 and treatment of subclinical mastitis is complicated and can vary among animal species,
332 individual animals and milk price, drug cost and availability of medicine.

333 Based on the current study, infection reduced milk production by approximately 20% in
334 the two sheep breeds and by 7% in the Murciano-Granadina goats. Moreover, the milk
335 quality as measured by SCC decreased. These losses are greater than those estimated in
336 other studies in sheep and goat (Leitner et al., 2004a,b, 2008) in which it ranged from 4 to
337 13% for Assaf sheep and from 1 to 2% for Saanen, Shami and crossbreeds goats with 25 to
338 75% udder infection. Martí De Olives et al. (2013) reported 15 and 38% milk loss in
339 subclinical IMI of Manchega dairy sheep at the short-term in early lactation, using whole
340 udder or half-udder models, respectively. Additionally, estimated curd loss by IMI varied
341 between 5 and 16% in sheep and 3 to 10% in goats (Leitner et al., 2008).

342 In conclusion, subclinical infection caused mainly by *S. aureus* and various CNS species,
343 resulted in lower milk yield and decreased quality. Bacteria colonies or culture-negative
344 growth were repeatable throughout samplings, and bacteriology and real-time PCR had
345 100% agreement. It should be emphasized that one sampling may not be sufficient to
346 determine IMI and therefore, other inflammatory responses should be monitored.
347 Moreover, when PCR methodology is used, aseptic and precise milk sampling procedure is
348 the key for avoiding false positive amplifications. However, sampling is problematic
349 because in many cases no inflammation signs appear and diagnostics by BAC or DNA
350 methods are expensive. Moreover, while identifying the bacteria is the beginning of the
351 process, it is important only if treatment and/or prevention of new infection are feasible.

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419

420 Table 1. Average daily milk throughout the experiment and somatic milk count (SCC) of
 421 dairy sheep and goats according to intramammary infection (IMI) status of the udder.

IMI status according to breed	No. Group	Milk, L/d		Log SCC	
		Mean \pm SE	Range	Mean \pm SE	Range
Manchega ewes,					
Uninfected	32	0.91 \pm 0.05 ^a	0.31 - 2.01	4.96 \pm 0.04 ^c	4.73 - 5.56
1 gland infected	17	0.82 \pm 0.06 ^{ab}	0.40 - 1.24	6.09 \pm 0.11 ^b	5.13 - 6.86
2 glands infected	7	0.72 \pm 0.08 ^b	0.35 - 1.24	6.80 \pm 0.11 ^a	6.38 - 7.27
Lacaune ewes,					
Uninfected	26	1.45 \pm 0.07 ^a	0.44 - 2.24	5.22 \pm 0.04 ^c	4.78 - 5.64
1 gland infected	17	1.26 \pm 0.11 ^{ab}	0.50 - 2.28	6.11 \pm 0.04 ^b	5.49 - 7.07
2 glands infected	9	1.06 \pm 0.10 ^b	0.50 - 1.50	6.56 \pm 0.14 ^a	5.61 - 7.05
Murciano-Granadina goats,					
Uninfected	8	1.39 \pm 0.15 ^x	1.14 to 1.65	5.55 \pm 0.03 ^b	5.30 - 6.23
1 or 2 glands infected	15 ^Z	1.14 \pm 0.13 ^y	0.78 - 1.68	6.18 \pm 0.06 ^a	5.67 - 7.01

422 ^{a, b, c}Means within the same breed with different superscript differ at $P < 0.05$.

423 ^{x, y}Means within the same breed with different superscript tended to differ at $P < 0.10$.

424 ^ZIncluding 3 goats with both udder halves infected.

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428 Table 2. Summary of the number of bacteria found in bacterial cultures [BAC1: Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB, Bellaterra, Spain) and
 429 BAC2: Interprofessional Milk Laboratory of Catalonia (ALLIC, Cabrils, Barcelona, Spain)] and real-time PCR (RT-PCR) using clinical and
 430 subclinical sheep and goats mastitic samples.

Item	NBF ¹	CNS	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Streptococcus</i> spp.	<i>Arcanobacterium pyogenes</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Enterococcus</i> spp.	<i>Enterobacteriaceae</i>
BAC1	30	38	8	5	2	2	3	2
BAC2	30	38	8	5	2	2	3	2
RT-PCR								
<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.	1	19	1	—				
<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp. and β -lactam	—	17	—	—				
<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp. and <i>Staph. aureus</i>	—	1	7	—				
<i>Streptococcus agalactiae</i>				—				
<i>Streptococcus dysgalactiae</i>				—				
<i>Streptococcus uberis</i>	—	1	—	—				
<i>Arcanobacterium pyogenes</i>				—	2	—	—	
<i>Peptoniphilus indolicus</i>						—	—	
<i>Enterococcus</i> spp.						—	3	
<i>E. coli</i>						2	—	—

¹No bacterial finding.

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432

433 **Figure captions**

434 Figure 1. Average log SCC in dairy goats (A) and dairy sheep (B) dairy according to
435 intramammary infection (IMI) status classified by the presence of bacterial infection and
436 inflammation in one (○) or two (●) udder-halves or with no bacterial finding (▲).

437

438 **Figure 1**

439 A. Dairy goats

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450 B. Dairy ewes

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